

ICCT

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE
ON CHEMICAL TECHNOLOGY

8th International Conference on Chemical Technology

May 3 – 5, 2021

proceedings

MAIN PARTNER

PARTNER

SPONSORS

MEDIA PARTNERS

Chemické listy

CHEMAGAZÍN

Proceedings of the 8th International Conference on Chemical Technology

1st edition, September 2021

EDITORS

Martin Veselý

University of Chemistry and Technology, Prague
Technická 5
166 28 Prague 6, Czech Republic

Zdeněk Hrdlička

University of Chemistry and Technology, Prague
Technická 5
166 28 Prague 6, Czech Republic

Jiří Hanika

Institute of Chemical Process Fundamentals of the CAS, Prague
Rozvojová 1/135
165 02 Prague 6, Czech Republic

Jaromír Lubojacký

Jistebník 242
742 82 Jistebník, Czech Republic

All communications submitted were duly reviewed by the scientific committee.

PUBLISHED AND DISTRIBUTED BY

Czech Society of Industrial Chemistry
Novotného Lávká 5
116 68 Prague, Czech Republic

in cooperation with
Czech Chemical Society
Novotného Lávká 5
116 68 Prague, Czech Republic

ISBN 978-80-88307-08-2

Copyright © 2021 Czech Society of Industrial Chemistry

SCIENTIFIC COMMITTEE

Assoc. Prof. Ing. Jaromír Lederer, Ph.D. | UniCRE Litvínov (President)
Prof. Ing. Jiří Hanika, Ph.D. | ICPF of the CAS, Prague (Vice-President)
Prof. Dr. Ing. Karel Bouzek | UCT Prague
Prof. Dr. Fabio Fava | Department of Civil, Chemical, Environmental and Materials Engineering, University of Bologna
Assoc. Prof. Ing. Tomáš Hlinčík, Ph.D. | UCT Prague
Prof. Ing. Milan Hronec, Ph.D. | STU Bratislava
Prof. Ing. Ľudovít Jelemenský, Ph.D. | STU Bratislava
Prof. Ing. Tomáš Jirout, Ph.D. | CTU in Prague
Prof. Ing. Jan John, Ph.D., FJFI, CTU in Prague
Prof. Ing. Petr Kalenda, Ph.D. | FCHT University of Pardubice
Prof. Elena Korotkova | Tomsk Polytechnic University
Assoc. Prof. Ing. Milan Králik, Ph.D. | VUChT Bratislava
Prof. Flavia Marinelli | University of Insubria, Varese, Italy
Dr. Agustín Martínez | Universidad Politécnica de Valencia
Prof. Ing. Petr Mikulášek, Ph.D. | FCHT University of Pardubice
Ing. Jozef Mikulec, Ph.D. | VÚRUP Bratislava
Prof. Dimitry Murzin | Åbo Akademi University, Turku, Finland
Prof. Ing. Lucie Obalová, Ph.D. | VŠB TU Ostrava
Prof. Ing. Josef Pašek, Ph.D. | UCT Prague
Prof. Dr. Ing. Petra Patáková | UCT Prague
Ing. Ivan Souček, Ph.D. | Association of Chemical Industry of the Czech Republic
Prof. Ing. Ján Šajbidor, Ph.D. | FCHPT STU Bratislava
Prof. RNDr. Pavel Šajgalík, DrSc. | Slovak Academy of Sciences, Bratislava
Prof. RNDr. Jitka Ulrichová, Ph.D. | UP Olomouc
Prof. Ing. Kamil Wichterle, Ph.D. | VŠB TU Ostrava
Prof. Ing. Petr Zámotný, Ph.D. | UCT Prague

PROGRAM COMMITTEE

Ing. Jaromír Lubojacký, MBA | Ixa Consulting Jistebník (President)
Assoc. Prof. Ing. Jaromír Lederer, Ph.D. | UniCRE Litvínov (Vice-President)
Prof. Ing. Jiří Hanika, Ph.D. | ICPF of the CAS, Prague (Vice-President, Best Poster Award)
Prof. Ing. Petr Zámotný, Ph.D. | UCT Prague (Petrochemicals and Organic Technology)
Assoc. Prof. Ing. Karel Ciahotný, Ph.D. | UCT Prague (Gas, Coal, Fuel)
Prof. Dr. Ing. Karel Bouzek | UCT Prague (Inorganic Technology)
Prof. Dr. Ing. Petra Patáková | UCT Prague (Biotechnology)
Ing. Barbora Branská, Ph.D. | UCT Prague (Biotechnology)
Prof. RNDr. Bohumil Kratochvíl, DSc. | UCT Prague (Pharmaceutical Technology)
Ing. Miloslav Slezák, Ph.D. | FCHT University of Pardubice (Waste Processing, Air and Water Protection, Technologies for the Decontamination of Soils)
Prof. Ing. Lucie Obalová, Ph.D. | VŠB TU Ostrava (Waste Processing, Air and Water Protection, Technologies for the Decontamination of Soils)
Prof. Ing. František Babinec, Ph.D. | RISCO Brno (Secure Management Processes, Accidents Prevention, etc.)
Prof. Dr. Ing. Dalibor Vojtěch | UCT Prague (Material Engineering)
Ing. Ivan Souček, Ph.D. | Association of Chemical Industry of the Czech Republic (Economy of Chemical Industry)
Prof. Ing. Tomáš Jirout, Ph.D. | CTU in Prague (Chemical Processes and Devices)
Ing. Hugo Kittel, Ph.D., MBA | UCT Prague (Oil, Petrochemicals, Biofuels)
Assoc. Prof. Ing. Antonín Kuta, Ph.D. | UCT Prague (Polymers, Composites)

CONTENTS

OIL, PETROCHEMICALS, BIOFUELS

UTILIZATION OF SYNERGIES BETWEEN TRADITIONAL OIL REFINERIES AND BIOREFINERIES AS AN IMPORTANT FACTOR IN THEIR FURTHER DEVELOPMENT

Kittel H.

CO-PYROLYSIS OF FISCHER-TROPSCH WAX VACUUM RESIDUE WITH HYDROCRACKING PRODUCT

Karaba A., Rozhon J., Filip L., Zámstný P.

PARTIAL HYDROGENATION OF DOUBLE BONDS IN POLYUNSATURATED FATTY ACID METHYL ESTERS

Slezáčková M., Mikulec J., Blaško J.

MODELING OXYGEN PRODUCTION VIA CRYOGENIC AIR SEPARATION

Poláková N., Variny M.

ALTERNATIVE USAGE OF MSCR TEST FOR EVALUATION OF TYPE AND CONTENT OF THE USED POLYMER

Jiša P., Černý R.

COMPATIBILITY OF MARINE FUELS CONTAINING ALTERNATIVE MATERIALS

Schlehöfer D., Vráblík A.

CO-PROCESSING OF PYROLYSIS PRODUCTS

Dlasková Jaklová K., Zbuzková B., Vráblík A.

HYDROGEN PRODUCTION OPTIMIZATION IN REFINING INDUSTRY

Cibulka T., Variny M.

GAS, COAL, FUEL

INDUSTRIAL COMBINED HEAT AND POWER PLANT REPOWERING PROPOSAL

Kšíňanová M., Variny M.

MATERIAL ENGINEERING

PHONOLITE. AN AVAILABLE, NATURAL CZECH RESOURCE FOR PRODUCING NOVEL VALUABLE MATERIALS

Hidalgo-Herrador J.M., Tišler, Z., Frątczak J., de Paz Carmona H., Velvarská R., Kocík J.

DECARBONISATION OF THE CHEMICAL INDUSTRY IN LIGHT OF GREEN DEAL

Souček I.

CHITIN-CAFFEINE MODELS IN BIOCIDAL WOOD COATINGS

Kobetičová K., Böhm M., Ďurišová K., Nábělková J., Černý R.

BINDING INTERACTIONS OF METHYLXANTHINES TO BEECH WOOD

Kobetičová K., Böhm M., Černý R.

COMBINED EFFECTS OF ADSORPTION AND PHOTOCATALYSIS ON MODEL DYE AO7 REMOVAL FROM AQUEOUS MEDIA USING TiO₂-LDH NANOCOMPOSITES

Starukh H., Petryk I., Matějová L., Martaus A.

MODELING OXYGEN PRODUCTION VIA CRYOGENIC AIR SEPARATION

Poláková N.¹, Variny M.¹

¹*Department of Chemical and Biochemical Engineering, Faculty of Chemical and Food Technology, Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava, Radlinského 9, 812 37 Bratislava, Slovak Republic
miroslav.variny@stuba.sk*

Abstract

Industrial-scale oxygen production is vital for many industrial branches. Current technologies exhibit a rather large specific power consumption, exceeding 150 kWh per ton of pure oxygen. With several of them being mature for decades, while others being still in development, possibilities for further energy consumption decrease should be exploited, to make the oxygen production via air separation more sustainable. With this long-term goal a model Cryogenic Air Separation Unit (ASU) is considered as a case study. First, its performance as a stand-alone plant is modeled and verified. Second, options for its improvement are identified and discussed, including heat recovery option from hot compressed air. The considered heat recovery project can be economically feasible, with the expected simple payback period of 6 to 13 years. The presented case study and its results contribute to sustainable industrial-scale oxygen production goal, while retaining a favorable production economy and exploiting the potential of carbon footprint reduction.

Introduction

Oxygen is the second most used gas in industry. It is used in food, chemical, oil industry, pharmacy, and others, with varying purity, state, and quantity requirements. Industrial praxis appreciates its contribution to carbon footprint lowering in oxycombustion application^{1,2} whether in power and heat production sector^{3,4}, or in light metals melting and processing^{5,6}. Its use in those applications offers at the same time potential for better process control⁷ and for carbon capture and storage^{8,9}.

To separate individual components of air, most air must be liquified. Gas can only be liquified at temperatures and pressures below its critical point; critical point of air is at $T_c = 132.5$ K and pressure $P_c = 37.7$ bar. Two liquefaction cycles are known, namely Linde and Kapica cycle.

There are two different ways of producing oxygen: non-cryogenic and cryogenic production route^{10,11}. Non-cryogenic separation methods include membrane processes and pressure swing adsorption, both operated at ambient temperature.

Study objectives

Several goals are defined in this work.

- Design a process scheme based on literature research
- Determination of the required theoretical stages
- Enthalpy and material balance of system
- Calculation of the duty of the heat exchangers, expander, condenser/vaporiser
- Estimation of heat recuperation potential from hot compressed air

Air Separation Unit (ASU) description

Cryogenic separation method is based on different boiling points of mixture components. This method was invented by Carl von Linde and was first used in industry in the 20th century. Distillation columns used for the separation are placed in “cold boxes” where the temperature is very low. Thermodynamic minimal work of oxygen separation from air is equal to 53.1 kWh per ton of oxygen. In 2015, the most efficient ASU exceeded the minimum energy three times¹².

The designed scheme according to Figure 1 can be divided into three sections. The first section provides air compression and water removal. In this work, air is considered as a three-component mixture composed of nitrogen, oxygen, and water vapor. Due to the process layout, it has to be compressed to the pressure of 6 bar which is done by two-stage compression, with an intercooler and final cooler, both serving as partial condensers of water vapor at the same time. The rest of the water vapor is removed in an adsorber. Air leaving the adsorber is divided into two streams, in a ratio to be estimated.

Both streams enter the main heat exchanger, where they are pre-cooled by process effluents. One fraction of air proceeds through the expander, where it expands to the pressure of 1.5 bar and flows to the upper column. The second stream flows directly to the lower column.

The third section includes a separation column and a secondary heat exchanger. The column consists of a low-pressure column (LPC) which is the upper column, and a high-pressure column (HPC). Condenser of nitrogen vapors in HPC serves as the LPC reboiler. A part of the condensed nitrogen is used as a reflux for HPC. The main product is oxygen, obtained in the lower part of LPC. The secondary heat exchanger serves as a pre-cooler for streams that serve as refluxes for LPC.

Figure 1. Designed scheme of cryogenic air separation

Model assumption and equations

Real equilibrium data are obtained by the Peng-Robinson thermodynamic model in AspenPlus software. Isobaric X-y equilibrium diagrams were constructed, and the number of theoretical stages required was determined using the McCabe-Thiele method¹³.

The first section involving compression and removal of water vapor is calculated by a set of equations. Mass flow of dry air, \dot{m}_G , is calculated by equation (1)

$$\dot{m}_G = \frac{\dot{m}_1}{1 + \bar{Y}_1} \quad (1)$$

where, \dot{m}_1 is the mass flow of air ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$), and \bar{Y}_1 is the relative mass fraction of water vapor ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$). Since air is compressed by two-stage compression, it is necessary to estimate the optimal pressure ratio, β , employing equation (2)

$$\beta = \sqrt{\frac{P_{fin}}{P_0}} \quad (2)$$

where, P_0 is the initial pressure (Pa), and P_{fin} is the final pressure (Pa). Compressor power input is calculated by equation (3)

$$P_n = \frac{R \cdot T \cdot \left(\frac{\dot{m}_G}{M_G} + \frac{\dot{m}_G \cdot \bar{Y}}{M_{H_2O}} \right) \cdot \frac{n}{n-1} \cdot \left(\beta^{\frac{n-1}{n}} - 1 \right)}{\eta_c} \quad (3)$$

where, R is the molar gas constant ($8.314 \text{ J}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$), T is temperature (K), M_G is the molar mass of dry gas ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$), M_{H_2O} is the molar mass of water ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$), n is the polytropic coefficient, and η_c is the overall compression efficiency.

Air cooling after compression carries away nearly all energy supplied by the compressor; thus, it would be beneficial to recover a part of it^{10,14}. In this sense, heat recovery for hot water production is devised by means of installing an additional heat exchanger upstream of each water cooler. The water is heated from a temperature of 60°C to 80°C , it being assumed that this water temperature will ensure its year-round use. After the first heat exchanger air is assumed to cool down to 65°C . The assumed pressure loss was 2 % of the air pressure at the inlet to the device. The reference state was chosen for the balance of the compression part: 0°C , g, 100 kPa. The enthalpy balance of intercoolers in which water does not condense is as follows (4)

$$\dot{H}_{input} - \dot{H}_{outlet} = \dot{m}_{H_2O} \cdot c_p \cdot \Delta T \quad (4)$$

where \dot{H}_{input} is the enthalpy flow of the stream entering the intercooler and \dot{H}_{outlet} is the enthalpy flow of the stream leaving the intercooler, \dot{m}_{H_2O} is the mass flow of cooling water, c_p is specific heat capacity and ΔT is the temperature difference at the outlet and inlet to the heat exchanger.

The enthalpy balance of intercoolers in which water does condense is provided by equation (5)

$$\dot{H}_{input} - \dot{H}_{outlet} - \dot{H}_{H_2O} = \dot{m}_{H_2O} \cdot c_p \cdot \Delta T \quad (5)$$

where \dot{H}_{input} is the enthalpy flow of the stream entering the intercooler and \dot{H}_{outlet} is the enthalpy flow of the stream leaving the intercooler and \dot{H}_{H_2O} is the enthalpy flow of the condensed water.

The heat exchanger parameters in which heat is recovered were calculated for the summer period. It has been considered that the cold medium, the water, flows in the tubes. For the hot medium, a forced flow was assumed when bypassing the bundle of tubes arranged one behind the other in a direction perpendicular to the axis of the tubes in the inter-tube space of the heat exchanger without compartments.

The price of a new heat exchanger C_E is calculated according to the equation (6)

$$C_E = C_B \cdot \left(\frac{K}{K_B}\right)^M \cdot CEPCI_{HX} \cdot \frac{\text{€}}{\text{\$}} \quad (6)$$

where C_B is the price of the basic heat exchanger in the reference year, K_B basic capacity, K is the capacity of the new heat exchanger, $CEPCI_{HX}$ is the ratio of the values of the CEPCI (The Chemical Engineering Plant Cost Index) indices in year X and in the reference year¹³.

The total investment costs of C_F are calculated according to the equation (7)

$$C_F = C_E \cdot (f_M \cdot f_T \cdot f_P \cdot (1 + f_{PIP})) + C_E \cdot (f_{ER} + f_{INST} + f_{ELEC} + f_{UTIL} + f_{OS} + f_{BUILD} + f_{SP} + f_{DEC} + f_{CONT} + f_{WC}) \quad (7)$$

where f_M is material factor, f_P is pressure factor, f_T is temperature factor, f_{PIP} is piping factor, f_{ER} is equipment erection factor, f_{INST} is instrumentation factor, f_{ELEC} is electrical factor, f_{UTIL} is utilities factor, f_{OS} is off-sites factor, f_{BUILD} is buildings factor, f_{SP} is site preparation factor, f_{DEC} is design and engineering factor, f_{CONT} is contingency factor, f_{WC} is working capital factor. All these factors were considered because this part of factory is to be built on "green field".

Model results and discussion

In this work, mass flow of air entering the first compressor of $30 \text{ t}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ is considered, with the inlet temperature of 300.15 K and the assumed mass fraction of water vapor of 0.01711 . The McCabe-Thiele method helps to determine the number of theoretical stages for each part of the column. For HPC it is 4 stages and for LPC it is 6 stages. The calculated mass flow of condensed water vapor ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$) in each condenser and adsorber is summarized in Table I. It is assumed that air leaving the adsorber is dry. Material balance is summarized in Table II.

Mass flow of produced oxygen gas, \dot{O} , is $5,760 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ with the purity of 95 %. Stream \dot{N} is almost pure nitrogen, which can also be used as inert gas if ASU is integrated in a refinery, or it can be supplied to other consumers.

The power input of both compressors is approximately the same and reaches 953 kW per item. This leads to specific power consumption for oxygen production of over 325 kWh per ton of oxygen. In a similar study¹¹, 22.58

MW electric energy are consumed to drive the compressors of a cryogenic air separation unit which produces 68.48 t/h oxygen. This yields specific power consumption of 330 kWh per ton of oxygen. Another study¹⁵, employing a much more integrated plant design, arrived at a value of 229 kWh per ton of oxygen, while pointing out possibilities for further improvement. We can thus conclude that the results of our calculations match well with those published in reference literature but at the same time it is obvious that there is still a substantial potential for oxygen production process efficiency increase.

Table I
Balance of water vapor in the studied process

Mass flow \dot{m} (kg.h ⁻¹)	Humidity \bar{Y} (kg.kg ⁻¹)
$\dot{m}_3 = 181.3$	$\bar{Y}_1 = 0.01711$
$\dot{m}_6 = 192.7$	$\bar{Y}_4^{eq} = 0.01096$
$\dot{m}_8 = 130.7$	$\bar{Y}_7^{eq} = 4.43 \times 10^{-3}$

Table II
Material balance of the studied process

Stream Nr.	Mass flow \dot{m} (kg.h ⁻¹)	Stream Nr.	Mass flow \dot{m} (kg.h ⁻¹)
10, 13, 14	8,998	22, 23, 24	10,020
11, 12	20,497	25, 26, 27	10,477
15, 16 (\dot{N})	20,690	28 (\dot{O})	105
17, 18, 19 (\dot{N})	2,940	29, 30 (\dot{O})	5,760
20, 21	21,196	31	11,176

Duties of individual heat exchangers and the separation column were also calculated using the enthalpy balance. The duty of the secondary heat exchanger is 159 kW while that of the main heat exchanger is 1,824 kW and that of combined condenser/vaporizer is 994 kW. The amount of work produced in the expander is 45 kW. This work can be used in compressors, and thus net power consumption of compressors will lower to the value 316 kWh per ton of oxygen. The calculated reflux ratio, based on the material and enthalpy balance, is 1.1154. The total amount of heat recovered for the summer period, 6 months, is 13,548 GJ, which at a heat price of 6 €/GJ, represents a saving of 81.3 thousand €. After deducting the cost of additional electricity consumed, the total savings for the summer period is 64.9 thousand €. The total amount of heat recovered for the winter period, and thus 6 months, is 6,198 GJ, which represents a cost saving of € 37.2 thousand. After deducting the cost of additional electricity consumed, the total savings for the winter period is 22 thousand €. The total expected annual saving is 86.9 thousand €.

Based on the assumed heat exchanger, the overall heat transfer coefficient will be in the range from 60 to 200 W.m⁻².K. The price of the heat exchanger was calculated for two limit values of this range. The results of the calculations can be found in Table III.

Table III
Economic analysis

Overall heat transfer coefficient U related to the surface area of the tubes (W.m ⁻² .K)	Surface area of the tubes A (m ²)	Main equipment cost C_E (€)	Total investment cost estimate C_F (€)	Simple payback period
60	460	177 thousand	974 thousand	13.2 year
200	138	78.1 thousand	429 thousand	5.8 year

Conclusion

Based on the literature survey and process material and heat balances, a cryogenic air separation unit was designed, yielding 5,760 kg.h⁻¹ of oxygen gas with the purity of 95 % vol. The mass ratio of streams 10 and 11 of 0.439. A literature search found that for operations of approximately the same size, this ratio was 0.14.

It was demonstrated that the mixture of oxygen and nitrogen does not behave as an ideal mixture; therefore, its modeling as a real mixture was necessary. Using the McCabe-Thiele method for both ideal and real mixture, the theoretical number of stages in HPC and LPC was estimated.

Since the amount of supplied air is $30 \text{ t}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$, which has to be compressed from 1 bar to 6 bar, two-stage compression was assumed with the calculated power input of both compressor stages being approximately the same, 953 kW. The power input of compressors is too high compared with the most efficient air separation units operated nowadays, so further optimization is needed. This is one of the long-term goals. Enthalpy balance of the separation column and heat exchangers provided their heat duties as 159; 1,824; 994 and 45 kW for the secondary heat exchanger, the main heat exchanger, the combined condenser/vaporizer and the expander, respectively.

The expected total heat recovery from hot compressed air to hot water is 19,746 GJ per year, which represent savings about 118.5 thousand €. Annual electricity costs will increase by 31.6 thousand €. The achievable net annual savings is therefore 86.9 thousand €. The prize of the additional heat exchanger was calculated for the two limit values of overall heat transfer coefficient. For the lowest value, the total investment is 974 thousand € and for the highest 429 thousand €. The simple playback period for the first one is 13.2 year and for the second one it is 5.8 year. It can be concluded that, under circumstances, heat recovery by hot water production can be a feasible means of operation expenses reduction.

Acknowledgement

This research was supported by the Slovak Research and Development Agency under the contract Nr. APVV-18-0134.

References

1. Baukal, E. C. Oxygen Enhanced Combustion, second edition. CRC Press (2013).
2. Dzurňák R., Jablonský G., Varga A., Kizek J., Pástor, M., Lukáč L.: MATEC Web Conf. 168, 07016 (2018).
3. Shah I.A., Gou X., Wu J.: Energies 12, 1949 (2019).
4. Hendershot R.J., Lebrecht T.D., Easterbrook N.C.: Chem. Eng. Prog. 106, 57 (2010).
5. Dzurňák R., Kizek J., Jablonský G.: AIP Conf. Proc. 1889, 020007 (2017).
6. Gripenberg H., Johansson A., Torvanger K.: *Six years experience from low-temperature oxyfuel in primary and re-melting aluminium cast houses*. In: Suarez C.E. (eds) Light Metals. Springer, Cham (2012).
7. Yeromin A., Yeromina O., Lukáč L., Kizek J., Dzurňák R.: Acta Montan. Slovaca 23, 175 (2018).
8. Nemitallah M.A., Abdelhafez A.A., Ali A., Mansir I., Habib M.A.: Int. J. Energy Res. 43, 7790 (2019).
9. Tan Y., Douglas M.A., Thambimuthu K.V.: Fuel 81, 1007 (2002).
10. van der Ham L.V., Kjelstrup S.: Energy 35, 4731 (2010).
11. Ebrahimi A., Meratizaman M., Reyhani H.A., Pourali O., Amidpour M.: Energy 90, 1298 (2015).
12. Banaszkiwicz T., Chorowski M., Gizicki W.: AIP Conf. Proc. 1573, 1373 (2013).
13. Perry H.R.: *Perry's chemical engineers' handbook*. McGraw-Hill, Kansas (1997).
14. Smith A.R., Klosek J.: Fuel Process. Technol. 70, 115 (2001).
15. Fu, Ch., Gudersen, T.: Energy 44, 60 (2012).